

Four new rice varieties in Bangladesh

M.M. Ullah and N.A. Khondaker, Regional Agricultural Research Station, P.O. Hathazari, Chittagong, Bangladesh

Four new varieties (BR12, BR14, BR15 and BR16) were compared to popular short duration Purbachi and BRI for the first wet season crop.

Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 15 May and harvested in Aug 1985. Urea, triple superphosphate, and muriate of potash were applied at 80, 30, 35 kg NPK/ha. BR14 and BR12 produced the significantly highest yields, Purbachi the lowest. BR14 matured 6 d later than Purbachi but gave 38% higher yield (see table). □

Performance of new rice varieties at the Farming Systems Research site, Hathazari, Chittagong, Bangladesh, 1985.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Duration (d)
BR16	4.10 cd	124
BR15	4.28 bc	126
BR14	4.81 a	122
BR12	4.66 ab	128
BR1	3.68 cd	113
Purbachi	3.49 d	116

^aValues followed by a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level of probability.

Heritability of rolled leaf character

Shen Fu-Chen, Liu Chuan-Xiu, and Pan Jian-Hui, Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Guizhou Province, China

Heritability of the rolled leaf character has been found to be controlled by a pair of mainly recessive genes.

Using R503, R524, and R556, with the rolled leaf, as female parents, and Guizhou 2, Guang er ai 104, and Qian Yi 272, with a flat leaf, as male parents, we observed the F₁ and F₂ in 1984 and 1985.

In some combinations, the character seemed to be controlled by a pair of

genes but in other combinations, the rolled leaf character was controlled

by 14 pairs of dominant genes (see table). □

Inheritance of rolled leaf character in crosses. Guizhou, China, 1984-85.

Cross	F ₁ flag leaf	F ₂ flag leaf			χ ²	P>
		Rolled- leaf plants	Flat- leaf plants	Rolled:flat		
R503/Guizhou 2	Flat	138	445	1:3	0.5445	0.30
R503/Qian Yi 272	Flat	200	652	1:3	1.0577	0.30
R503/Guang er ai 104	Flat	135	391	1:3	0.1243	0.70
R524/Guizhou 2	Flat	126	456	1:3	3.4845	0.05
R524/Qian Yi 272	Flat	129	385	1:3	0.0025	0.80
R524/Guang er ai 104	Flat	194	610	1:3	0.3251	0.50
R556/Guizhou 2	Rolled	630	7	63:1	0.8885	0.30
R556/Qian Yi 272	Rolled	468	2	256:1	0.0140	0.90
R556/Guang er ai 104	Rolled	354	5	63:1	0.0410	0.80

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GRAIN QUALITY

Grain quality of some promising mutants

M.A. Sagar and M. Ashraf; Rice Grain Quality Lab, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad, Pakistan

We examined the physicochemical characteristics of two mutants developed at the Nuclear Institute for Agriculture and Biology, Faisalabad. DM16-5-1

from Basmati 370 has significantly higher yield (29.16%) than its parent. FG6 from IR6 has higher head rice recovery (8%) than its parent.

No significant differences were found between parent and mutant for 100-grain weight, grain length, breadth, size and shape, elongation ratio, amylose content, and gelatinization temperature. However, the length to breadth ratio for both groups differed

Quality characteristics of milled rice of mutants and their parents. Islamabad, Pakistan.

Characteristic	Aromatic			Non-aromatic		
	Basmati 370	DM16-5-1	Statistical significance ^a	IR6	FG6	Statistical significance ^a
100-grain weight (g)	1.5	1.5	NS	1.8	1.8	NS
Grain length (mm)	6.6	6.6	NS	7.0	1.2	NS
Grain breadth (mm)	1.6	1.7	NS	2.0	1.8	NS
Length: breadth	4.2	3.9	S	3.6	4.0	S
Grain size and shape	Long Slender	Long Slender	—	Long Slender	Long Slender	—
Cooked grain length (mm)	13.3	12.4	S	13.2	13.4	NS
Elongation ratio	2.0	1.9	NS	1.9	1.8	NS
Chalkiness score	5.0	8.0	HS	5.0	1.5	HS
Whiteness	40.4	41.2	NS	46.0	42.8	S
Amylose content (% dry basis)	20.0	19.3	NS	29.6	28.1	NS
Protein content (% N × 5.95)	8.4	7.3	HS	8.0	7.2	HS
Alkali spreading value	5.2	4.3	HS	7.0	7.0	NS
Gel consistency (mm)	46.8	50.8	HS	59.8	47.5	HS
Gelatinization temp (°C)	70.5	72.1	NS	67.0	66.0	NS
Aroma	Strong	Moderately strong		None	None	

^aS = significant at the 5% level, HS = significant at the 1% level, NS = nonsignificant.